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Research Article

In Vitro Anthelmintic and Hemolytic Potential of Lantana Camara: A Pharmacological Study

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ABSTRACT

To study and investigate the L. camara Leaves for their anthelmintic and hemolytic activity using Earthworm(Eisenia Fetida) and human erythrocytes, respectively. Methods: The different successive extracts, i.e., chloroform, ethanol, and aqueous extract of L camera leaves, were used on E. fetida as a test worm. The other concentrations (250,500,750µg/ml) of various extracts were tested for bioassay, which involved the determination of paralysis and death time of worms. Albendazole was used as standard, and normal saline was used as a control. Hemolytic activity was carried out by different solvent extracts (chloroform, hexane: ethyl acetate, aqueous, pet ether) and Vit C as a standard drug. Results: The anthelmintic activity of the leaves LC is done using different extracts like aqueous, ethanol, and chloroform. The chloroform extract gave higher anthelmintic activity than the aqueous extract, and the hemolytic activity of the leaves LC is done using different solvent extracts like chloroform, hexane: ethyl acetate aqueous and petroleum ether. There is no activity of aqueous extract but petroleum ether shows more activity. Conclusion: In this study, we reported that L. camara leaf extract in the presence of chloroform has more anthelmintic activity than Albendazole suspension (Synthetic drug). This concludes that the L. camara plant leaf is more beneficial and active than albendazole. The hemolytic activity of L. cameraleaves aqueous extract and its various solvent fractions revealed that the leaves possess no hemolytic activity in aqueous extract but show high hemolytic activity in the presence of petroleum ether, which can be further used to isolate bioactive compounds.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants represent an important source of medically important compounds; since ancient

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times, medicinal plants have been used to cure several health problems. Systemic analysis of these plants provides a variety of bioactive molecules for the development of newer pharmaceutical products.^[1] LC is a native of tropical America but now occurs throughout the Philippines in thickets and wastelands at low and medium altitudes.^[2] LC was probably introduced into India before 19th century, currently LC is found throughout India and known by different name viz, Raimunivya (Hindi), Chaturangi and Vanacehedhi (Sanskrit), Arippu and Unnichidi (Tamil), Aripoov, Poochedi, Konginipoo and Nattachedi (Malayalam), Thirei, Samballei and Nongballei (Manipuri), Tantani and Ghaneri (Marathi), Pulikampa (Telegu), Kakke and Natahu (Kannada).^[3-4]

LC is a flowering ornamental plant. It is used in several traditional medicinal preparations and is well-known for curing several diseases. From ancient times, flowers were used as pectoral for children, leaves and fruits of that plant can be used externally for various skin diseases, cuts and wounds, and stems and roots are used for gargles and toothaches as a toothbrush.^[5-7] It was traditionally used diaphoretic, carminative, Antispasmodic, tonic, and Antiemetic to treat respiratory infections and disorders (cough, cold, asthma and bronchitis) in the treatment of tetanus, epilepsy, dysentery and gas trophy.^[8] LC belongs to the family Verbenaceae. It is also known as wild sage, Surinam, Tea plant, Spanish flag and West Indian Lantana. Different parts of LC are reported to possess essential oil, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, carbohydrates, proteins, alkaloids, glycosides, phenyl ethanoic, oligosaccharides, quinine, saponins, steroids, triterpenes, sesquiterpenoids and tannin as major phytochemical groups.^[9-12] Parasitic worms (helminths) of the gastrointestinal tract are pathogens of paramount global importance. Over a billion people, mainly in developing countries,

are transmitted to be infected with soil-transmitted helminths. At the same time, helminth infection is also a serious problem in livestock production worldwide, causing significant economic losses and threatening food security.^[13]

The word "anthelmintic" is from the Greek word "anti," which means "against," and helminths means "worm," which means to kill or wipe out worms or parasites. Anthelmintics are drugs that either kill (vermicide) or expel (vermifuge) infesting helminths. Helminthiasis or helminth infection is a parasitic disease of humans and other animals in which part of the body is infected with parasitic worms. They often live in the gastrointestinal tract of their hosts but may also stay in other organs. Scientific studies have shown that many plants used in human ethnomedicinal practice showed huge pharmacological activities. The human body, GIT, is the abode of many helminths, but some also live in tissues, or their larvae migrate into tissues. They harm the host by depriving them of food, causing blood loss, injury to organs, intestinal or lymphatic obstruction, and secreting toxins.^[14]

The toxicity of the active molecule is a key factor in the design, and hemolytic activity represents a useful starting point in this regard; it provides primary information on the interaction between molecules and biological entities at the cellular level. The haemolytic activity of any compound is an indicator of general cytotoxicity towards normal healthy cells.^[15] Usually, saponins present in the plants showed hemolytic activity by creating changes in the erythrocyte's membrane.^[16]

Plant extracts can positively affect the red cell membrane, and many plants have serious adverse effects, which include induction of hemolytic anaemia. Therefore, many commonly used plants must be evaluated for their potential hemolytic activity.

Aim and Objectives

Aim: This study aims to investigate the *L. camara* Leaves for their anthelmintic and hemolytic activity using Earthworm (*Eisenia Fetida*) and human erythrocytes, respectively.

Objective:

- To present the Anthelmintic activities and potential health benefits of *Lantana camara*.

- To perform the Hemolytic activity of *Lantana camara*.

To provide an overview of the chemical composition of *Lantana camara*.

Plant Profile

Fig .1. *Lantana camara*

Scientific name: *Lantana camara*

Synonym: Spanish Flag, Tick berry, Shrub Verbena, Kakke, Chadurangi

Biological source:

It is an ornamental flowering plant of *Lantana camara* Linn belonging to the Verbenaceae family.^[17]

Botanical classification^[18]

Kingdom: Plantae

Subkingdom: Tracheobionta

Super division: Spermatophytat

Division: Magnoliophyta

Class: Magnoliopsida

Subclass: Asteridae

Order: Lamiales

Family: Verbenaceae

Genus: *Lantana*

Species: *L. camara*

Eisenia fetida

Fig No. 3

Scientific classification

Domain: Eukaryote

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Annelida

Clade: Pleistoannelida, Sedentaria.

Class: Clitellates

Order: Opisphopora

Family: Lumbricidae

Genus: *Eisenia*

Species: *E. fetida*

Synonyms: *Eisenia foetida* (older spelling)

Eisenia fetida, known under various names such as manure worm, redworm, brandling worm, panfish worm, trout worm, tiger worm, red wiggler worm, etc.,^[28] is an earthworm adapted to decaying organic material. These worms thrive in rotting vegetation, compost, and manure. The red wiggler is reddish-brown, has small rings around its body, and has a yellowish tail.^[29] Groups of bristles (called setae) on each worm segment move in and out to grip nearby surfaces as it stretches and contracts its muscles to push itself forward or backward. *E. fetida* worms are native to Europe but have been introduced (both intentionally and unintentionally) to every other continent except Antarctica.^[30]

Life span

The lifespan of *E. fetida* under controlled conditions varies between one and five years.^[31]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material: In July, the plant was collected from Chadachana in Vijayapura district -586204, Karnataka. The plant is authenticated by Dr. Ajit Lingayat, Director of Shri B.M.K Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya. After authentication, fresh leaves material was collected, cleaned, and shade dried.

Worm collection: Indian earthworms *E. Fetida* were used to study anthelmintic activity.

The earthworms were collected from Patil Organic Manure, Earthworms and Dairy Farms and washed with water. Earthworms of 3-5 cm in length and 0.1-2cm in width were used due to their anatomical and physiological resemblance with the intestinal roundworm parasite of human beings.

Extract preparation: The leaves were pulverized by a mechanical grinder and passed through a 20-mesh sieve. The powdered leaves were extracted successively using chloroform (Soxhlet), ethanol, and aqueous (maceration) extract. The extracts were filtered through a cotton plug, followed by Whatman filter paper. The extract was evaporated under reduced pressure using a Rota evaporator at a low temperature of 40^o- 50^oc until all the solvent had been removed to give an extract sample. Then the weight of each residue was recorded.^[17]

Phytochemical screening: Phytochemical screening was carried out for all the extracts per the standard protocol. Plants were screened for alkaloids, carbohydrates, Flavonoids, oil and fats, proteins and tannins.

1. **Alkaloids:** 20 ml of distilled water was added to 2 gm of the powdered plant sample, boiled in a water bath, and filtered. About 10 ml of this filtrate was mixed with 5 ml of Wagner's reagent and shaken vigorously for a stable, persistent froth. The Reddish Brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

2. **Carbohydrates:** 100 mg of the plant extract was dissolved in 5 ml of water and filtered. To 0.5 ml of the filtrate, 0.5 ml of Benedict's reagent was added and heated in a boiling water bath for 3 minutes. A characteristic colour indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

3. **Flavonoids:** To a portion of the filtrate, 10 ml of ethyl acetate was added and heated in a water bath and filtered. 1 ml of dilute ammonia solution was added to the filtrate and shaken well. A yellow coloration indicates the presence of flavonoids.

4. **Oil and fats:** A small extract was pressed between the two filter papers. Oil stain on the filter papers indicates the presence of oils and fats.

5. **Proteins:** The plant powder was extracted in different solvents, and solvent-free plant extract was mixed with a few ml of diluted HCl and filtered. Two drops of ninhydrin solution (10 mg of ninhydrin in 200 ml of Acetone) were added to the filtrate. The mixture was mixed properly. The purple color indicates the presence of Proteins and Amino acids.

6. **Tannins:** The powdered plant sample pinch was mixed with 5 ml of water. The mixture was boiled in a water bath and then filtered. A few drops of 0.1% ferric chloride were added to the filtrate. Brownish green or a blue-black coloration indicates the presence of tannins.^[18]

Anthelmintic activity

The different concentrations (250µg/ml, 500µg/ml, and 750µg/ml) of Chloroform, ethanol extract and aqueous extract were prepared. All the earthworms were washed into a standard saline solution. At room temperature, two or three nearly equal-sized earthworms were placed in each Petri dish. All test, standard and control dilutions were placed in the three petri dishes. Observations were

made for the time taken to paralyze (paralysis was said to occur when earthworms did not revive in normal saline) and death (death was conducted when earthworms lost their motility and followed by their body colors fading away).^[19]

Hemolytic activity

The heparinized human red blood 250 μ L was utilized for the assay. Washed with saline (0.9%) and then centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 min to remove plasma. Precisely 40% v/v suspension was made with isotonic phosphate buffer at pH 7.4, and it was used as an RBC stock solution for further hemolytic assay. The Hemolysis assay was followed (Henkelman, 2009) with modifications per previous studies (Lakshmegowda et al., 2020). In the reaction mixture, 10% erythrocytes hemolysis was induced by an equal volume of 100 mM AAPH containing samples 50 μ g/mL, without samples serves as the negative control, and normal

erythrocytes, i.e., without AAPH or extracts, serves as Blank. Similarly, 0.2% Triton (in PBS) is taken for 100% hemolysis as a reference control. The results were compared with standard L-ascorbic acid as a positive control. The reaction mixture was incubated for two h at 37°C and, at the end of incubation, diluted with eight volumes of PBS and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was collected, and the absorbance was read at 540 nm; the percentage of hemolysis was calculated.^[20]

RESULTS

Percentage yield: 50 gm of dried leaves powder of *L. camera* was extracted in sterilized distilled water to obtain the test extract. After drying, the filtrate yielded 3.05 gm of extract, which is 6.10% of the initial plant powder (50 gm)

Preliminary phytochemical determination

Table .1: Phytochemicals present and absent in various solvents of LC

Sr no	Phytochemicals	Chloroform	Ethanol	Aqueous
1	Alkaloids	-	+	+
2	Tannins	-	+	-
3	Flavonoids	+	+	+
4	Saponins	+	-	+
5	Carbohydrates	+	+	+
6	Steroids	-	-	-
7	Phenols	+	+	-
9	Oil and fats	-	+	-

Here, +: present, -: Absent

Fig. Phytochemical Test

Anthelmintic activity of *L. Camara*

Table.2: Estimation of anthelmintic activity

Drugs	Concentration	Paralysis time(min)	Death time (min)
Albendazole	250mg/ml	3.2	7.1
	500mg/ml	2.05	5.2
	750mg/ml	2.0	4.0
Aqueous	250mg/ml	2.5	3.56

Fig. Albendazole Suspension

Fig. Chloroform Extract

Fig. Anthelmintic activity graph

Hemolytic activity

Table 3: Estimation of Hemolytic properties of the sample

SI. No	Sample	Haemolysis (%inhibition)
1	Chloroform	44.07±3.60

2	Hexane: Ethyl acetate	36.24±3.35
3	Aqueous	No activity
4	Petroleum ether	65.27±1.73
5	Std. (Vit -C)	85.38±2.24

Fig. Hemolytic Activity Graph

DISCUSSION

The preliminary phytochemical qualitative analysis revealed the presence of secondary metabolites. Tannins, Flavonoids, Saponins, Carbohydrates, phytosterols, and Alkaloids are present in aqueous extract. Tannins, Flavonoids, Carbohydrates, Alkaloids Oil and fats are present in Ethanol extract, and Flavonoids, Saponin and carbohydrates are present in the chloroform extract of *L. camara*. The ethanolic, chloroform and aqueous extract of leaves of the plant's LC was evaluated for its anthelmintic potential in the present investigation. It is evident from the experimental data that the chloroform extracts of the *Lantana camara* showed significant anthelmintic activity when they were comparable with the standard drugs, Albendazole, at the same concentration.

Hemolytic activity of the leaves of LC aqueous extract does not show any hemolytic activity. But Petroleum ether shows higher activity than other extracts like chloroform, hexane: ethyl acetate by using standard Vitamin C.

CONCLUSION

Lantana camara is an essential medical plant with several medicinal uses in folk and traditional medicinal systems. Based on the present result and available report, *Lantana Camara L.* has a powerful anthelmintic, which is confirmed, and an aqueous extract displaced pro found anthelmintic activity in the study. The anthelmintic activity of *Lantana camara* can be attributed to bioactive

compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins, which have been reported to have anti-parasitic properties. Based on the present result and available report, *Lantana Camara L.* has a powerful anthelmintic, which is confirmed, and an aqueous extract displaced pro found anthelmintic activity in the study. The anthelmintic activity of *Lantana camara* can be attributed to bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins, which have been reported to have anti-parasitic properties.

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